

Artificial Intelligence in Indian Banking Sector

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OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 6

Special Issue : 1

Month : August

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Kumar, P. S. Charan.
“Artificial Intelligence
in Indian Banking
Sector.” *Shanlax
International Journal
of Arts, Science and
Humanities*, vol. 6, no.
S1, 2018, pp. 248–50.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.1403633](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1403633)

Abstract

In India Artificial Intelligence is not new this concept is from many years but the new improvement in AI Adaptation as increasing in technology. The technology itself is getting better day by day with various applications. As everyone thinks about CHAT-BOTS only as AI service but many other adaptations are there as it related to services to customer. SBI has a major role in adaptation of artificial intelligence as it is the largest bank in India (As per the Accenture Banking Technology vision 2018 Report). From decades research institutions and universities have been working with various AI technologies especially in the field of Social Transformation. In Banking Sector the AI reduces the cost for customer interaction and increases there efficiency.

Keywords: Adaptation of AI in Mobile Cheque Deposit by customer in ICICI Bank, Self Passbook Printing Machine by Customer itself, Cash Deposit Machine installation by banks, and other AI robots in banking Sectors.

Introduction

The Research is fully based on Primary source (survey based on Employees of bank and Customers). The research is aim toward the opportunities and other drawbacks of AI in banking sectors. The Survey form is attached to the paper at last. Major Bank Taken for survey: Canara Bank CANDI Branch M.G.Road Bangalore.

Technology in India is increasing day by day in banking sectors. As the number of customers increasing AI adaptation also increasing but it is not new to India in technological field. In the branch it is the first Digital where they have adopted robot “CANDI” to provide an end to end digital experience to the gen-next customer.

The bank provides every facility as other bank provides but the difference here is fully upgraded with Robots. The survey has taken on the basis of primary data at Canara Bank M.G.Road, Bangalore.

I have visited the branch where the robot will explains the information about branch. The manager of CANDI Canara bank explained that the branch is opened for the basically IT based people in M.G Road where they can use the banking facility from morning 08.00am to 08.00pm at night. The bank is fully digitalized and Robot is helps in using the Digital systems.

Objective of the Study

- To know about the usage of Artificial intelligence in India
- To get aware about the merits and demerits of Artificial Intelligence.
- Numbers of people aware about AI
- Drawbacks of Artificial Intelligence.

In my research of CANDI Canara Bank M.G Road Manager Mr. Justine J Mathew explained me about the usage and implementation of Robot for the help of customer in their branch.

Observation

I have observed that the bank is suitable for only those people who knows about the digital process of bank and people who don't know about digital process of bank for them ROBOT is Installed where they can ask the queries. The list of segment wise deposit is given below:

Parameters	June 17	Sep 17	Dec 17	Mar 18	Jun 18	Growth (%)
Total Deposits	485905	496440	503888	524722	533274	9.75
Current Deposit	22489	23623	23245	24894	21185	(5.84)
Saving Deposits	126586	131456	134341	142051	141466	11.75
CASA Deposits	149084	155080	157586	167035	162651	9.10
Term Deposits	336821	341360	346302	357737	370622	10.04
RTD	207180	213258	214848	212800	214094	3.30

The saving deposits diagram shown in the below diagram as in increasing continuously

Methodology

I have used the methodology of collecting primary Data from CANDI br and some secondary data from newspapers and other international journals. In the research it found that the method of survey is suitable for this and I have spoken with some of the customers of Bank that how they are getting the facility of Bank.

Artificial Intelligence in other field

As per the latest information Japan is adopted Artificial Intelligence in Teaching. It is reportedly cost of a \$227,000. 500 children’s in Japan will get the English- Speaking robots. The move comes ahead of a chance in the national curriculum in two years that will require children from the age of 10 to learn English. This implementation is because of lack of teachers in school level in Japan. Japanese schools struggle to find qualified teachers for English classes and lack the cash to hire trained assistants. Some primary schools already turned to technology, introducing English-speaking robots in the classroom. As English classes are compulsory for Japanese student aged between 12 and 15 and starting age will be reduced in 2020

Budgetary pressures may lead to search for technological solution by policy makers in education. The quote from Steve jobs, Apple co-founder- “The most important thing is a person. A person who incites your curiosity and feeds your curiosity; and machines cannot do that in the same way that people can.

Conclusion

As compare to other nation India is also in the same track in adopting the Artificial Intelligence in various fields like Bank, Hotels, and other places. The main problem in India in SERVER which is not supports very time as in my research found many times CANDI Robot hangs as it needs server backup and another problem is that the Employment to human will reduce as Robots comes in the field. Every work cannot be done by ROBOTS but some places where ROBOTS can take place of Human.

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